

THE LITERARY IMAGE OF MENTOR AND STUDENT IN SUFI LITERATURE

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Abstract. The current article is devoted to the common views to the literary images of mentor and student in eastern Sufi literature. Moreover, the paper covers some significant information and opinions on the topic from the literary works of Makhmud Shabistari, namely, Gulshani Raz. There are focused mainly two English translations of Gulshani Raz; by Edward Whinfield in XX century and Florence Lederer in XX century. The investigations are based on qualitative research and methodology.

Key words: mentor, student, consultation, poetry, prose, wisdom, nobleman.

To understand the reasons for their presence in Eastern literature, it is necessary to discover the unique literary contexts in which mentor and student interrelate, performing various functions. From antiquity, the figure of the mentor has undergone a variety of changes. Only the basic characteristic - his connection with the teacher - have remained unchanged across the ages. Many reasons may underlie the perpetuation of the image of the mentor. Indeed, he/she could play any role, representing the whole range of human potentials and possibilities. Over the centuries, mentor's name and image could undergo changes, ranging from that of teacher to one's own sacred figure, or even up to the moment of spiritual creation itself.

The literary character of "mentor and student" or "master and disciple" has been amply presented in Eastern literature over the past two thousand years. Even in ancient times, a special type of personality was given the name "mentor." Each period in the history of Eastern literature and ideas produced its own unique characterizations, whether in folklore, epics, novels, or other genres. The essence of this interaction never appears superficial: it helps reveal, sometimes in depth, the personality of mentor and student, as well as the relationships between them. This is the reason behind the metaphysical and historical sense in so many student-mentor or mentor-creator relationships that exist frequently among different cultures of the world.

In eastern, especially in Sufi literature, mentorship is stressed significantly and each writer or author always rely on other mentors ideology. For example, Rumi approached to Ghazali in most cases, and coming to Shabistari, Ibn Arabi was mentor and teacher in Sufi world. Shabistari then describes the process of descent of the One after the manner of ibn 'Arabi. The first manifestation of the essence is the universal reason ('aql al-kulli), the stage of unity (ahadiyyah); the second is the universal soul (nafs al-kidli). Then come Throne ('arsh), the heavenly Chair (kursi), seven heavenly spheres, four elements, the three kingdoms of minerals, vegetables, and animals. The last in the series is man who is the acme of creation. Though temporally the last in the series, man is logically the first, as tree is potentially prior to the seed. All the world was created for him while he was created for himself, as the embodiment of God's highest manifestation. But he possesses certain baser elements which, however, are essential for his moral progress. A mirror, to be able to reflect things, must have one side totally blackened. If it were all crystal, it would cease to serve as a mirror.

Mentorship in Eastern Classics is described as role singularity and identifies various elements that encourage positive student-mentor interactions. Mentors in these classic texts are older, wise individuals who pass on advice to friends, family, and students through the development of discourses on societal roles, rules, temperament, knowledge, and dignity, and mentorship.

We can find more sample masterpieces in Eastern literature which reveal mentorship and concept of nobleman in the example of prophets. One of them is Gulshani Raz by Makhmud Shabistari. Shabistari follows the general trend of mystic writers in describing the nature of saintship (wildyah) and prophethood (nubuwoah). Saintship is a more general category than prophethood. Saints so called and prophets are all saints in the first instance. In a mystic saintship is hidden, while in a prophet it is manifest. A saint is a follower of the prophet in Law and in this he attains the highest position and becomes equal to the prophet in realizing union with the Lord. With the death of the Holy Prophet the first cycle of saintship, a cycle in which prophethood and saintship were both manifest in the world, came to an end. After the Final Prophet, saintship continued and the new cycle began to take its shape. One day the seal of saints will appear, who shall be the acme of saintship and, with his appearance, the cycle of the two worlds will come to an end. He will be the whole, of which all the previous saints were parts. Like the "Seal of the Prophets," he shall be a blessing to the whole world. He will succeed in bringing peace and security to man;

justice and equity will reign. The word "seal," according to ibn 'Arabi, does not signify a mystic with whom saintship will come to an end, but with Shabistari, the seal of saints, like the "Seal of Prophets," would terminate saintship for ever. The last of the saints is the "seal" with whom the world will come to an end.

Another Asian texts related to the concept of mentorship point to more than guidance provided by the mentor, suggesting even a type of intimacy, fraternity, or family. In Confucian classics such as the Book of Rites, where a father at age seventy shares his wisdom and recycles his "disciples" gifts to relatives, and the Analects, where the intimate father-son laws could be with professors with their mentors, guidance, trust, and communication are seen as positive qualities between the scholarship and the student. The Hindu Bhagavad Gita is about a chat between Lord Krishna and Arjuna, his cousin and student, during the latter's emotional plight. The nobleman and his charioteer are none of the characters. Taoism is about communication and component parts. The correspondence includes Confucius, Buddha, and Krishna, as well as Plato. None of these characters plays a role. Allah is Ablai's mentor in the classic Muslim Spiritual Reports, where he is the universal II-Man. In the Koran, the meaning "in the name of Allah the MOST MERCIFUL, the MOST COMPASSIONATE" originates from compassion and sociability and is inserted at the beginning of the letters. There are guidelines on consultation and the importance of properly guiding society in separate Sura. A good student is acknowledged by a great teacher, a statement that has a broader implication for students seeking motivation.

Our more extensive and definitive attempts to examine the substantial and broad repercussions of the rhetoric of the Odyssey also established the significance and consequences of terms that served as paradigms for comparison, using selected pretexts. Furthermore, whereas our central focus was almost always the detailed and subtle relationships between the narrator and opposing characters, it became clear that these relationships have some very tangible repercussions in the denouement. In the present topic, we have restricted our area of examination. We wish to acknowledge the fact presented by some studies that the Mentor, along with the physical complexity presented by the character, would somehow feature complexly within the same space and time. Pursuing this direction seems far too simplistic to overlook in the subtle art of establishing paradigm fields, or metaphorical spaces of reference.

Scholars note that both Mentor and Telemachus play significant roles in the intermediate processes between poetry and prose, on a substantial level. Similarly, they exert a considerable effect in comprehensive training and

development, serving as the model for training and the concept for development. By dwelling on some extremely significant points in the comprehensive epics that present these correlations, we managed to establish the significance and specific nature of the partnership between the writer and his work, and we established carefully chosen meanings that can be re-appropriated.

To conclude, we use the relationships between Mentor, student and their respective "others" — Antinous and Zeus — to level criticism against the comprehensive approach, related to the personal change both in the society of the readers brought about by the formidable nature of the written text, or what would be written, and the influence that is exerted on the writer by the written text in question.

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